

LLM-MultiAgent System: A Cooperative LLM Architecture for Automated Requirements Elicitation

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LLM-MultiAgent System

The LLM-MultiAgent System aims to contribute to the area of Requirements Engineering (RE), especially in the initial phase of requirements elicitation.

The main problems that the system aims to mitigate are:

- **Limitations** of traditional **RE methods**;
- **Limitations** of Large Language Models (LLMs) **used alone** in RE;
- Lack of systematic **evaluation of the synergy** between **LLMs and MultiAgent systems in RE**.

LLM-MultiAgent System | System Overview

- **LLM-MultiAgent integrates Gemini 2.5 Pro with two AI Agents:**
 - Recommender Agent;
 - NFR Expert Agent.
- **Coordinated by a central AI Core (Genkit AI);**
- **Uses Firebase-based Memory Module for context preservation.**

LLM-MultiAgent System | Key Functionalities

- **Natural language chat (text or voice) with file upload support;**
- **Automatic extraction of Functional and Non-Functional Requirements;**
- **Validation interface before final report generation;**
- **Export of results to PDF.**

LLM-MultiAgent System | Architecture

LLM – MultiAgent System

The application

LLM-MultiAgent System | How the Agents Work?

- **Recommender Agent:** Enhances user inputs, manages dialog;
- **NFR Expert Agent:** Detects, enriches and recommends Non-Functional Requirements;
- **AI Core:** Central processing of enriched prompts;
- **Memory Module:** Contextual support from prior data.

LLM-MultiAgent System | Sequence Diagram

LLM-MultiAgent System | Access and Execution

- **Source Code:** *github.com/moaathalshaikh/LLMReqMultiAgent*
- **Hosted on Google Cloud Platform**
- **APIs, Firebase Project, and Frontend Deployment**
- **Local setup instructions available in the GitHub repository**

LLM – MultiAgent System

The application - App screens

LLM-MultiAgent System | Main interface

LLM-MultiAgent System

About Us Services Admin

Agent Dialogue

Hello! I'm LLM-MultiAgent System. You can select a domain, ask me questions, describe your system, or upload a document (PDF, TXT) to discuss its requirements. How can I help you today?
10:16:56 AM

Type your message or 'extract requirements'...

Start Over

Start New Conversation

Developed by: [Moaath ALSHAIKH](#) 2025

Note:

- To reduce hallucinations and random results, the system will run a **temporary RAG** during the chat session.
- The system will extract requirements only from the text in the chat and the files uploaded within the chat. However, the retrieved information cannot be relied upon for other sessions.

LLM-MultiAgent System | Main interface with features

Note:

- **Support three Languages:**

We note the ability to switch between three languages (English, the default system language, Portuguese, and Arabic).

- **Voice Input:**

The voice-based text input feature can be used for all three languages.

- **Attach File:**

A file can be uploaded during a chat, enhancing and facilitating the user's input of information.

LLM-MultiAgent System | Start the conversation and replying from “Recommender Agent”

The screenshot displays the LLM-MultiAgent System interface. At the top, there are navigation buttons for 'About Us', 'Services', 'Admin', and a search icon. The main area is titled 'Agent Dialogue' and shows a conversation. The first message is from the system: 'describe your system, or upload a document (PDF, TXT) to discuss its requirements. How can I help you today?' (12:29:47 PM). The second message is from the user: 'hello, I would like to design platform for my University' (12:30:42 PM). The third message is from the recommender agent: 'That sounds like a great project! To help me understand your needs better, could you please provide more details about the platform you envision for your university? Specifically: 1. What are the primary goals of this platform? (e.g., improving communication, facilitating learning, streamlining administrative tasks) 2. Who are the intended users of this platform? (e.g., students, faculty, staff, alumni) 3. What are some of the key features you would like to include?' (12:30:45 PM). At the bottom, there is a text input field with the placeholder 'Type your message or 'extract requirements'...', a send button, and a green button labeled 'Extract Requirements Now'.

Note:

- When a conversation starts, the Recommender Agent will respond to the user,
- Asking them questions and making suggestions that will enrich the conversation.

LLM-MultiAgent System | “Expert NFR Agent” Suggestions

The screenshot displays the LLM-MultiAgent System interface. At the top, there is a header with the system name and navigation links for 'About Us', 'Services', 'Admin', and a search icon. The main area is titled 'Agent Dialogue' and contains a chat window. The chat window shows three messages:

- A blue message from the Expert NFR Agent: "The users are Professors, Students, and attendance" (12:42:29 PM).
- A white message from the Recommender Agent: "Okay, so the users will be Professors, Students, and for attendance purposes. To make sure I understand correctly, could you clarify a few things: 1. When you say 'attendance', do you mean attendance tracking is a key feature, or are you referring to a specific user role related to attendance? 2. Are there different levels of access or permissions needed for each user type (Professors, Students, Attendance personnel)? 3. Are there any other types of users to consider (e.g., administrators, guest lecturers)?" (12:42:31 PM).
- A yellow message from the Expert NFR Agent: "[Expert NFR Insight - Usability]: Considering these different user types, how important is ease of use and accessibility for each group?"

At the bottom of the chat window, there is a text input field with the placeholder text "Type your message or 'extract requirements'..." and a blue send button. Below the chat window, there is a green button labeled "Extract Requirements Now".

Note:

- During the conversation, the second agent, the Expert NFR Agent, is inactive, listening to the responses provided by the Recommender Agent.
- When Expert NFR Agent notices any text in the chat that suggests a non-functional requirement, it displays an alert message advising the user to focus on this non-functional requirement.

LLM-MultiAgent System | Extracted Requirements

The screenshot displays the LLM-MultiAgent System interface. At the top, there are navigation buttons for 'About Us', 'Services', 'Admin', and a search icon. Below the navigation bar, a message indicates an attached file: 'Requirements Gathering and User Stories_ORACLE.docx.txt'. The main content area is titled 'Extracted Requirements' and contains a table with the following data:

ID	Description	Type	Priority	Validation
REQ001	The system must allow PGCOMP professors and PhD students to register using their UFBA email, student ID, and a strong password.	Functional	High	✓ ✕ ✎
REQ002	The system must validate the UFBA email and student ID during registration.	Functional	High	✓ ✕ ✎
REQ003	The system must enforce a strong password policy (minimum 8 characters, including at least one letter and one number).	Non-Functional		✓ ✕ ✎

A notification box at the bottom right of the interface states: 'Requirements Extracted 72 requirements extracted successfully.'

Note:

- At any point during the conversation, the user can click the "Extracted Requirements Now" button. The system will then extract functional and non-functional requirements based on the conversation between the user and the files uploaded during the conversation.

Important note:

- The number of requirements extracted will vary in each new conversation we have with the system, even if we use the same conversation or files.
- This is because the system is based on the concept of Generative AI, and therefore generates them differently in each new conversation.

LLM-MultiAgent System | Generate Report and Download extracted results

LLM-MultiAgent System

About Us Services Admin

Generate Report

Review and finalize the dialogue summary and traceability links, then download your report.

Dialogue Summary

--- Requirements Extracted ---
The requirements outline the functionalities for a conference management system (WEPGCOMP). Key features include user registration (professors, students, attendees), administrator roles and privileges, presentation submission and scheduling, voting and awards, certificate issuance, homepage content, and multi-edition event hosting. The system must also ensure security and data validation. Some

Download JSON Download CSV Download PDF Report

Note:

- After extracting the requirements, we can go to the "Generate Report" section, review the generated report, and view a "Dialogue summary" of the chat.
- We can download the extracted results in several formats, such as PDF, JSON, and CSV.

LLM-MultiAgent System | Validation with Stakeholder

LLM-MultiAgent System

About Us Services Admin

Extracted Requirements

ID	Description	Type	Priority	Validation
REQ001	The system must allow PGCOMP professors and PhD students to register using their UFBA email, student ID, and a strong password.	Functional	High	
REQ002	Editing done.	Functional	High	
REQ003	The system must enforce a strong password policy (minimum 8 characters, including at least one letter and one number).	Non-Functional	High	 Mark as Rejected / Delete

Note:

- The results can be reviewed with stakeholders, experts, or developers, where we can approve, delete, or modify the requirement,
- then we can upload a new output file and compare it with the old one.

Confirm Deletion

Are you sure you want to delete requirement 'REQ002'?

Cancel

Yes

LLM – MultiAgent System

RESULTS

LLM-MultiAgent | Results of the 5 dialogues realized

Results	FR	NRF	FR-H	FR-M	NFR-H	NFR-M
Base Line (46)	40	06				
★ Result Dialog I (87)	-	-	70	14	2	1
Result Dialog II (63)	-	-	58	1	1	3
Result Dialog III (105)	-	-	82	12	10	1
Result Dialog IV (59)	-	-	57	0	0	2
Result Dialog V (47)	-	-	45	-	1	1

FR-H or NFR-H – Requirements with priority High
 FR-M or NFR-M – Requirements with priority Medium

LLM-MultiAgent | Categories – Justification

Categories	Justification
1. User Registration and Authentication	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Focuses on account creation and secure access for specific user roles.▪ Relates to validation of user identity at the time of registration.
2. User Roles and Privilege Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Involves control over administrative permissions and user role assignments.▪ Defines automatic role assignment upon user registration.
3. Presentation Submission and Organization	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Directly linked to submission of presentation content for the event.
4. Evaluation and Certification	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Involves evaluation processes tied to submission quality.▪ Relates to certificate issuance following event participation or contribution.
5. Event Sessions and Scheduling	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Focuses on building and managing the event agenda and session logistics.
6. Event Edition Management and Administration	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Supports administrative control over each instance of the event.
7. Interface and Usability	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Concerned with usability and user experience, including responsive design.
8. Non-Functional Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Describes security properties, a classic non-functional requirement.

LLM-MultiAgent Extraction | Dialog 1

Category (possible new agents)	Base line		type equivalence (extraction dialog 1)		
	FR	NRF	Full	Partial	No Match
1. User Registration and Authentication	7	-	6	7	0
2. User Roles and Privilege Management	11	-	10	6	1
3. Presentation Submission and Organization	7	-	6	1	1
4. Evaluation and Certification	6	-	6	15	0
5. Event Sessions and Scheduling	5	-	6	9	0
6. Event Edition Management and Administration	2	-	4	2	0
7. Interface and Usability	2	-	2	4	0
8. Non-Functional Requirements	-	6	0	1	7
TOTAL	40	6	40	45	9

LLM-MultiAgent Extraction | Type equivalence

- **Full** - Two requirements are considered fully equivalent when they convey exactly the same functional intent and outcome—covering identical scope, roles, and conditions—despite any minor differences in wording or structure, and when a clear, unambiguous one-to-one mapping exists between them.
- **Partial** equivalence occurs when two requirements overlap but differ in scope—one is narrower, broader, or adds extra constraints or details to the other.
- **No match** indicates the two sets have no overlapping requirements; the functionality or logic is entirely distinct.

LLM-MultiAgent Extraction | Performance in requirements elicitation

Metrics	Base line	LLM-MultiAgent
▪ Total registration	46	
▪ Functional requirements	40	
▪ Non-functional requirements	6	
▪ True positives (full)	-	40
▪ False positives (partial)	-	45
▪ False negatives (No match)	-	9
▪ Accuracy	-	81,63 %
▪ Recall	-	47,06 %
▪ F1-score	-	59,70 %

True Positives

- All 40 FRs were correctly identified.
- Strong performance in explicit, action-oriented requirements.

Partial False Positives

- 45 requirements classified as 'False Positives (partial)'.
- Many represent useful implicit requirements.
- May enrich the requirements base with additional information.

False Negatives

- 9 gold standard requirements were not identified.
- Most are NFRs – highlights the need for contextual improvements.

LLM-MultiAgent System | Threads to Validity

- **Internal Validity:**

- Prompt Bias;
- Model Bias;
- Subjective Evaluation.

- **External Validity:**

- Limitations of Experimental Scenarios;
- Impact on LLM Performance;
- Interface-Specific Constraints.

- **Construct Validity:**

- Evaluation Metrics;
- Limitations of Metrics;
- Contextual Nature of Requirements;
- Interpretive Layer in Classification.

- **Mitigation Strategies:**

- Iterative Prompt Design;
- Task Decomposition;
- Multi-Annotator Human Evaluation;
- Logging and Replay.

LLM-MultiAgent System | Final Considerations

- **LLM-based systems enhanced with multi-agent support show significant potential for requirements engineering, especially in:**
 - Early-stage requirements analysis.
 - Automated categorization.
- **Practical benefits:**
 - Reduction of manual effort in analyzing extensive textual artifacts.
 - Support for multidisciplinary teams in understanding requirements.
 - Encouragement of documentation standardization.
- **Critical limitation:** requires human validation and contextual adaptation to avoid bias and misinterpretations.

LLM-MultiAgent System | Future Works

- **Generalization to other software domains:**

1. Apply the system to critical, embedded, and regulated domains (e.g., safety-critical systems).

- **Comparison across multiple LLMs:**

1. Incorporate additional models (e.g., GPT-4o, Claude).
2. Conduct systematic comparisons between different LLMs.

- **Prompt refinement and personalization:**

1. Dynamically optimize prompts.
2. Adapt to the user's linguistic style.

- **Longitudinal studies:**

1. Assess the tool's impact across the entire software development life cycle.
2. Provide robust evidence of its practical value.

LLM-MultiAgent System | Activities Developed

Member	Activities Developed
Moaath Alshaikh	Design and coding of the LLM-MultiAgent System - Publication in the Github Repository - Extractions of RFs and RNFs for analysis of results - Participation in the preparation and review of the documents produced (Article, Tutorials and Presentations).
Ricardo Vieira	Literature Review – Preparation of the Article and Tutorial – Continuous review of the documents produced (Article, Tutorials and Presentations) – Discussions and Analysis of Results.
Clélio Xavier	Participation in the preparation and review of the documents produced (Article, Tutorials and Presentations) - Continuous literature reviews - Discussions and Analysis of the Results.
Samuel Mercês	Participation in the preparation and review of the documents produced (Article, Tutorials and Presentations) - Recording of the Video tutorial and publication on Youtube - Discussions and Analysis of the Results.

LLM-MultiAgent System | References

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LLM – MultiAgent System

Our Repositories

LLM-MultiAgent System | Our Repositories

On Github:

<https://github.com/moaathalshaikh/LLMReqMultiAgent>

On Google Cloud Platform:

<https://6000-firebase-studio-1746660239432.cluster-etsqrqvqyvvd4erxx7qq32imrjk.cloudworkstations.dev/>

On Zenodo:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15706945>